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CONSUMER LOYALTY PROGRAM, A STRATEGIC TOOL TO ATTRACT, RETAIN, MANAGE AND INFLUENCE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract:

Customer loyalty is all about attracting the right customer, getting them to buy, buy often, buy in higher quantities and bring you even more customers. However, that focus is not how we build customer loyalty.

We build loyalty by...

- *Keeping touch with customers using email marketing, thank you cards and more.*
- *Treating our team well so they treat our customers well.*
- *Showing that we care and remembering what they like and don't like.*
- *We build it by rewarding them for choosing us over our competitors.*
- *We build it by truly giving a damn about them and figuring out how to make them more success, happy and joyful.*

In short, we build customer loyalty by treating people how they want to be treated.

Key Words: Loyalty Cards, Consumer Buying, Living and Home Products

1. Introduction:

During this period of Economic slowdown, it is very important for each retail chain to formulate a strategy which will entice its customer to return which in return can help organization to increase its revenue enabling them to drive through this uncertain period. As such Loyalty card has become one for the most important medium to address this issue and for creating loyal customer who will be back for a return purchase. But the fact of the matter is that by just formulating a loyalty program an organization can't create loyal customer. Moreover it is seen that customer tends to buy just to get discount which in return affect the retail margin of an organization.

2. Problem under Study:

As such the current problem focuses on how an organization can make its loyalty program effective. It's well known fact that every organized retailer in the furniture industry segment has loyalty program similar to each other. In such a scenario where there is so many loyalty cards in circulation, the problem is that these loyalty programs are not creating ultimate loyalty among their customer as each of us are members of more than one loyalty program and looks for discount which are more attractive. So it's very important to know how much value an organization can add to its card in order to make its loyalty program competitive and effective.

Ensuring customer loyalty, enhancing it and effectively managing it is one of the most crucial factors impacting sales. It is no longer important to have a formal loyalty management application but it is equally imperative to move forward from the short term promotional campaigns to a well defined customer focused, relationship oriented programs

By studying the importance of loyalty cards it help the business gain competitive edge and can hence increase profitability. The retailers can ensure that their programs offer both value and other customer benefits. Understanding the effectiveness of loyalty cards option helps in customer retention.

3. Objective of the Study:

1. To study the customer loyalty program of a furniture retailer
2. To know in what way they attract their loyalty card holders for purchasing in their specialty store.
3. To know the effect of loyalty program on their customers.
4. To know whether the loyalty program of a selected retailer is creating loyalty among their customers.
5. To know whether the selected retailer is successful in making its customer loyal with the help of loyalty card.
6. To know the knowledge of the customer regarding the Loyalty card of selected furniture retailer.

4. Methodology:

The researcher has applied a combination of descriptive and exploratory research design. The research was conducted by using contact methods through questionnaire, interview and observation. The information was collected from the footfall of retail Store at Mantri Mall, Bangalore. Total numbers of customer walk-in at retail store during the entire period of ten days were 6,789 (Source: Internal). Out of the total population the sample taken among the respondents from the departments as well as customers and public is 200.

5. Literature Review:

Dick and Basu (1994) defined loyalty as a customer commitment to the brand or approach to the brand (service, product category, etc.). Loyalty is also interpreted as an expectation to continue a relationship with a particular brand (Wilson, 1995). According to Aaker(1991), brand loyalty is defined as "the attachment that a customer has to a brand".

According to Beerli et al.(2004) loyalty described based on inertia, when the user purchase brand again because he/she used to do it, however if the conditions allow the user will replace the product with the

competitors brand. He also stated that, a true brand loyalty when the decision to repeat purchase is made on satisfactory experiences and positive attitude toward the preferred brand. Generally loyalty has been explained as an active loyalty when a consumer re-use the brand and recommend the brand to the others, and a passive loyalty, that is characterized as an intention of not switching even when brand provides less positive conditions. (Neringa and Vilte, 2009).

Sharp and Sharp (1997) explain that in the last decade, loyalty programs gained considerable “practical and academic attention in the context of customer retention and customer relationship management” (P. 474). They further explain that the simple objective of any loyalty program is to reward loyal customer behavior with special services or rebates and, at the same time, to promote this loyal behavior in order to achieve the economic benefit of long-term business relationships.

Mr. Kotler (2003) writes: “Marketing is not the art of finding clever ways to dispose of what you make. Marketing is the art of creating genuine customer value. It is the art of helping your customers become better off. The marketer’s watchwords are quality, service, and value” (P XII). In his another definition of marketing, Mr. Kotler (2003) said “Marketing management is the art and science of choosing target markets and getting, **keeping**, and growing customers through creating, communicating, and delivering superior customer value” (P. XIII). This second definition gives a hint in the word ‘keeping’ as highlighted because it is with this purpose of keeping the customers that one of the marketing concepts ‘Loyalty’ was emerged.

Indeed, the companies in nearly all industries have recognized that acquiring new customers alone cannot insure a successful survival even though their advertisements have become more creative and more successful, according to Duffy (1998). Most companies now are paying more and more attention to their current customers because with rising number of new goods and services and new brand names, customers may easily switch to competitors. Therefore, turning the current customers into loyal customers, so that they keep coming back again and again, loyalty concept grew very popular as this is exclusively demonstrated in the works of Reichheld (1993), Duffy (1998), Sharp and Sharp (1997), Bolton et al. (2000) and many more authors.

Industry Positioning Map

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Gender of the Respondents

Interpretation:

From the above graph it clearly shows that 62% of male and 38% of female visit the retailer. Females normally purchase furnishing, home ware and décor items where as males buy bed, sofa, dining etc.

Age of the respondents

Interpretation:

It is interpreted that 5% of people are from age group of 16-25 yr, 37.5% of people are from the age group of 25-35yr,33.5% of people are from age group of 35-45yr,9.5% of people from age group of 45-55yr and 14.5% of people are of 55 yr and above visit retail outlet. By this we can analyze that the people of age group 25-35 and 35-45yr visit the outlet more in number for purchase.

Occupation of Respondents

Interpretation:

Here we can interpret that 9.5% of government employee, 52.5% of private or self employee,9% of housewife,14.5% of business man and 14.5% from other category people visit retail outlets to make the purchase. Here the people visiting retail outlet is more from the private or self employee sector as it is rating 52.5%.

Income of the respondents

Interpretation:

From the above graph we can find that income level of people is crucial in visiting retail outlets. Here 5% of people whose income level is 5000-15000,42.5% of people whose income level is 15000-30000,28.5% of people whose income level is 30000-60000,24% of people whose income level is above 60000 on monthly basis visit retailer outlet.

Awareness of retailer

Interpretation:

Here the means through which the awareness about retailer presence in the mind of customer is derived.14.5% of people from newspaper, 9.5% from hoardings,0% from radio,47.5% from friends,28.5% from other source came to know about retailer. Here one thing we can notice is that the means of radio for creating awareness about retailer is ineffective.

Frequency of Purchase

Interpretation:

It is observed people visit the outlet. 28.5% of people visit once in a month, 9.5% once in three months, 28.5% of people once in six months, 28.5% of people once in a year visit living store and 5% of people are first time visitors in living..

Factors influencing consumer buying

Interpretation:

It is viewed from the above graph that majority of people buy furniture in living because of quality, price, style, discount. Here 31.5% of people prefer quality, 21% of people prefer for style, 13% of people prefer for price and 16% of people prefer for discount available. people are giving least importance for service and loyalty scheme while furniture purchase.

Frequency of purchase due to loyalty program

Interpretation:

Here it is interpreted that do loyalty program encourage people to purchase frequently from a retail outlet. Here 76% of people are saying yes it will encourage and 24% of people are saying no loyalty program will not encourage purchasing often.

Preferred rewards and incentives

Interpretation;

Here which form of incentives or rewards people prefer is being analysed. 78.5% of people prefer cash discount, 4.5% of people prefer free promotional product, 13% of people prefer gift vouchers, only 4% of people prefer loyalty points. Here what we understand is that loyalty points scheme is not so effective and benefiting the customers in a bigger way.

Attractiveness of Loyalty Programs

Interpretation:

From the graph it is interpreted that the loyalty program conducted by retailer is attractive or no. 43% of people are saying yes the loyalty program is attractive, 9.5% of people are saying it's not attractive, 42.5% of people are not sure they are assuming it to be attractive and 5% of people are not being informed about the loyalty program of retailer.

Benefits preferred as loyalty rewards

Interpretation:

Here it is viewed that which form of rewards in the form of loyalty program is being preferred by customer so that it is going to benefit them. 39% of people prefer special promotions, 17.5% of people

prefer occasional free gift vouchers, 17.5% of people prefer birthday and anniversary special offers and 26% of people expect premium service as their loyalty benefit.

Product Comparison

Interpretation:

From the above graph we can view that which products of reliance living is attractive and better when it is compared with its competitor. 15.5% of people say that sofa is good, 9.5% of people vote for bed, 15.5% of people prefer dining, 9.5% of people say that décor is better, 22% of people vote for home ware products and majority of people that is 28% of people says that furnishing is better compared to its competitors.

Preferred Brand of Furniture

Interpretation:

From the above graph it is analyzed that which brand people normally prefer when they are going for the furniture purchase. Majority of people prefer buying from reliance living for furniture purchase ie,

58%.21% of people prefer Home Centre, 4% of people prefer @Home, 12.5% of people prefer buying furniture from Home Stop and 4% of people don't prefer any of these brands while purchasing furniture's.

Influencing factor in Brand Selection

Interpretation:

Here why people prefer buying furniture from the above selected brand is being analysed.23% of people prefer due to its style, 28.5% prefer because of its quality, 17% due to its pricing, 14.5% of people prefer for its discount, 8.5% of people prefer due to its location which influences him to buy. No person has preferred the above brand because of its loyalty scheme which shows that loyalty scheme is not so effective.

Reasons for Brand Switching

Interpretation:

From the above graph it is analyzed that when do people switch from one brand to another.35% of people says that when higher discounts are given they will switch to other brand.4.5% of people switch due to non-availability of the products and majority of people ie, 60.5% of people switch to other brand when more variants of products are available. And it is made clear that no customer is going to switch from one brand to another because of its higher loyalty points.

Rating of Reliance Living

Interpretation:

Here the rating is given to reliance living according to the customer perception. 14.5% has rated reliance living under 1-10 scale as 5 and 28.5% has given 8 points, 14% has given 6 points, 24% of people has given 7 points, 4.5% of people has given 9 points and 15% of people has given 2,3,&4 points.

Online communication preference

Interpretation:

It is desired to know whether online communication through social media helps you to get more information about the products of reliance living and whether it helps you to get the competitors products information in a better way is being analyzed. 52.5% of people says that it helps them, 24% of people who are not much exposed to the technology and price sensitive says no it will not help them and 23.5% of people are not sure but assume that it may be helpful or not helpful.

Recommendations to friends and relatives

Interpretation:

At the end it is being analyzed that whether customer has recommended the reliance living products to their relatives and friends or no.57% of people has recommended to their friends and relatives, 5% of people has not recommended to any one and 38% of people may be willing to recommend the reliance living products to their friends and relatives in the coming days.

8. FINDINGS

1. Consumers do not tend to increase their purchase from a particular store just because they have loyalty card of the same.
2. Consumers shop in stores which provide better discounts, regardless of whether they have loyalty card of the same.
3. Most of customers prefer reliance living because of its pricing structure which is lesser when compared with its competitors.
4. The customers visiting reliance living is more from the age group 30 – 45 who are middle age people.
5. The profitable customers for reliance living is more from the self employed people and people working in private companies may be their income is more so their disposable income is also high.
6. Here what we can find out by this report is that people are not giving importance to loyalty scheme or loyalty points as it is not benefiting them effectively during their purchase.
7. People prefer cash discounts and gift vouchers instead of loyalty points in their card.
8. There is demand for furnishing, home ware, dining, décor items more in reliance living.
9. Here the customer want loyalty program from reliance reliving to be conducted but not in the forms of points but in the form of discounts, special offers, gift vouchers.
10. One of the major finding is that customer switch from one brand to another due to higher discounts and more variants of products availability.
11. Most of the people want online facility through social media for better information about the reliance living and competitors product.
12. The sales of the reliance living per day is around 8-10 lakhs which is higher when compared with its competitors per day sales.

9. SUGGESTIONS

1. As the loyalty card scheme is being followed by all the brands and retail outlets only providing the loyalty card points is no where going to help the customers to become loyal to your brand.
2. Loyalty scheme adopted by a brand or the outlet should not be just to increase the sales but it has to retain the customers. It should to be done to maintain a long lasting relationship with the potential customers.
3. Loyalty program conducted by the brand is done in order to get the customer database and understand their buying behavior in order to create marketing campaign which in return will help in repeat purchase and increase the loyalty for the brand.
4. In order to get the potential and loyal customer for your brand, understanding the buying behavior of the customers and targeting them with suitable offering is very essential.
5. Conducted various engagement activity in-store for customer will increase the level of excitement within customers which will help the brand to retain them.
6. Once the customer make a purchase from reliance living in order to make him loyal we should follow up with him/her by sending him/her mails about the products information and feedback of the products which will create a kind of belongingness between the customer and the brand.
7. By giving special customized offers to customers during their birthday, anniversaries and on occasional days will help us in creating loyalty among customers.
8. In order to attract customer and create a perfect ambience for shopping brand should come up with high standard of visual merchandising with pleasant music and enhance the customer with pleasant fragrance and aroma which helps in stimulating the sensory organs of a person.
9. By understanding the buying behavior of the customer we can follow them by sending the product information through mails or SMS in which they are interested to buy which will help in creating a need in the minds of the customer.
10. Giving offers in those products in which the customer is interested makes sense which will help him to be loyal to our brand.
11. By giving premium service to the customer and by treating and receiving them well we can make them loyal to our brand

10. CONCLUSION

Now a day the retail sector is growing very rapidly and at a faster rate hence the competitors are more in order to sustain in this competitive market it is very essential for every retailer to be innovative compared to its competitor and maintain a good relationship with the customers. Maintaining good relationship with customer does not mean giving discounts and offers instead we need to understand the needs and requirements of the customer and create a want in them which will influence them in making a purchase as well as make them loyal to our brands.

As such, retailers are exploring ways to leverage technology such as predictive software to uncover subtle buying patterns and identify customers who may be likely to buy in categories they have never bought in before. Many are making greater use of the Internet to promote their loyalty program through accessible and informative Websites and targeted e-mail.

Usually local Kirana store owners knew their shoppers well and could easily anticipate needs. Today, large organized retailer use computers and data to help do the same. These include using loyalty programs to support community initiatives, encouraging staff to get to know customers personally, and otherwise making cardholders feel that the store values their business and respects their right to limit access to their personal information.

As customer loyalty being one of the most important factors for the business today, loyalty programs – loyalty card and other value added service, if well designed and implemented, can help the business gain competitive edge and can hence increase profitability.

